

A Sustainable Built Environment Through Pre-demolition Audit

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Abstract

Every building has a service life after which it becomes unsafe for the occupant and the public. Therefore, when a building or infrastructure has come to end-of-service-life a decision has to be made which is mainly demolition. This research identifies the importance of pre-demolition audits before embarking on the demolition process as this is crucial to selecting the right demolition method, procedure, and sequence of operation.

European Commission defined a pre-demolition audit as an activity planned by the building or infrastructure owner that results in the register of the materials and components resulting from the upcoming demolition or renovation projects, as well as their administration and recovery options. Comprehensive material inventories are useful in accounting for the estimated waste from the demolition of the building, pre-demolition audit is a practical tool to conduct material inventory. A pre-demolition audit is essential for managing resources and promoting recovery of the material with useful life inside.

This paper will explore the benefits of using pre-demolition audits to enhance the sustainable consumption of natural resources, and promotion of urban mining as a sustainable practice in the built environment. The methodology is a review of articles, documents, and technical reports on pre-demolition audits in the built environment.

The outcome of this research will promote the use of pre-demolition audits in managing construction and demolition waste and accurate material inventory for materials and products stored in existing buildings and infrastructure thereby extending their service life and reducing under-utilization of resources.

Keywords

Pre-demolition audit, resource efficiency, sustainable consumption, and urban mining.

Format

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